

BUCKLING AND VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF THIN-WALLED LAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAMS HAVING OPEN AND CLOSED SECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

An efficient modelling technique based on one dimensional beam finite element analysis for buckling and vibration of thin-walled laminated composite beams having open/closed sections is proposed in this paper. For the vibration analysis, the effect of axial load is also incorporated. The formulation is generalised so as to accommodate any stacking sequence of individual walls and consider all possible couplings between different modes of deformation. The effect of transverse shear deformation of walls and out of plane warping of the beam section is considered where the warping can be restrained or free. The incorporation of shear deformation in the finite element formulation of the beam has imposed a difficulty which is successfully addressed using a concept proposed by one of the authors. Numerical examples of open section I beams and closed section box beams are solved by the proposed approach and the results are compared with those available in literature to show the performance of the proposed method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modelling of thin-walled laminated composite beams having open and closed cross-sections as a condensed one dimensional beam model has drawn considerable attentions of many researchers in recent years. It leads to the development of a number of modelling techniques and their advancements which helped to have a better understanding of the behaviour of such beams under complex loading and boundary conditions. References 1-8 are simply few recent representative samples of these models. One of the early applications of this approach is found in the modelling and analysis of helicopter blades which is then followed by analysis of pultruded composite profiles, wind turbine blades and some similar structures.

The previous studies may be divided into two major categories based on the approach used for calculating the cross-section stiffness coefficients of these composite beams. The first approach is based on 'analytical technique' while the other approach utilizes a two-dimensional (2D) cross-sectional analysis based on a (2D) finite element model to calculate the cross-section matrices.

Hodges and co-workers [3] have significantly contributed toward the development of the second approach where the three dimensional (3D) elasticity problem defining the deformation of these beams is systematically divided into a one-dimensional beam problem and a two dimensional cross-sectional problem. This method is generally referred to as variational asymptotic beam section analysis (VABS) which is based on variational asymptotic method (VAM) [9]. This approach is also suitable for modelling solid and the thick walled cross-sections. The same group ([10-14]) have also attempted to solve the 2D cross-sectional problem defined within the framework of VAM analytically but this approach involves rigorous mathematical treatments to evaluate the cross-sectional stiffness coefficients.

In the present study, the analytical approach (first approach) is adopted for the determination of the cross-sectional matrices as the objective of this paper is to analyse thin-walled composite beams. Moreover, the 2D finite element analysis or a complex mathematical treatment involved with the other approach can be avoided in the present approach. Specifically, the current study has adopted the analytical approach proposed by Sheikh and Thomsen [8] and extended to buckling and vibration with/without axial load of these structures. The different modes of deformation and their coupling considered in the development of the present closed-form analytical solution are axial, torsion, bi-axial bending, bi-axial shear as well as warping for the torsional deformation. The cross-sectional matrices are explicitly derived for the open I section and closed box section. The present formulation considered both plane stress and plain strain conditions of a lamina. The 1D beam problem is solved by the finite element approximations. The out of plane warping displacement requires a C^1 continuous finite element formulation for the twisting rotation, which is accommodated using Hermetian interpolation functions. On the other hand, the usual treatment of the transverse shear deformation requires a C^0 formulation. This needs the reduced integration technique to avoid any shear locking problem. The different degrees of continuity for the different modes of deformation and their coupling impose a problem for their implementation. This problem is addressed satisfactorily utilising the concept proposed by Sheikh [15] which does not require the reduced integration technique. For the 1D beam finite element analysis, a three node beam element as shown in Fig.1 has been developed.

Figure 1: A typical beam element

A computer code is written in FORTRAN to implement present formulation. Numerical examples of thin-walled composite beams having different cross sections and other conditions are analysed by the proposed model and the results obtained in the form of buckling loads and vibration frequencies and validated with the available results in literature. These results demonstrate a very good performance of proposed finite element model.

1 FORMULATION

Figure 2 shows a segment of the composite beam shell wall where x - y - z is taken as the global Cartesian coordinate system and x is directed along the beam axis which is passing through the centroid of the beam section. A local orthogonal coordinate system x - s - n is also defined where x - n plane passes through the tangential plane of beam wall mid plane (local x -axis is parallel to the global x -axis) and n is directed along the wall thickness. The displacement components at the mid-plane of the shell wall in the local coordinate system (x - s - n) can be expressed in term of the global displacement components of the beam [1] as

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{u} &= U + y\theta_y + z\theta_z + \varphi\theta'_x, \\ \bar{v} &= V \cos \alpha + W \sin \alpha - r\theta_x, \\ \bar{w} &= -V \sin \alpha + W \cos \alpha + q\theta_x,\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where φ is the warping function, θ_x is the torsional rotation and θ_y , θ_z are bending rotations of the cross-section of the beam along x and y , respectively. These bending rotations can again be expressed as $\theta_y = -V' + \Psi_y$ and $\theta_z = -W' + \Psi_z$, where Ψ_y , Ψ_z are shear rotations of the beam section about z and y , respectively, and V' , W' and θ'_x are respectively the derivatives of V , W and θ_x with respect to x .

It has been observed that the warping displacement of a closed section beam is relatively less than that of an open section beam [14] but the present formulation has considered the effect of warping in

all cases. Considering the effects of bending and transverse shear deformation of the beam shell wall, the displacements at any point of the shell wall away from its mid-plane may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \bar{u} + n \left(-\frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial x} + \psi_{xn} \right), \\ v &= \bar{v} + n \left(-\frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial s} + \psi_{sn} \right), \\ w &= \bar{w}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where ψ_{xn} and ψ_{sn} are shear rotations of the shell wall section about s and x , respectively. It is assumed that $\psi_{sn} = 0$ whereas ψ_{xn} can be expressed in terms of the corresponding global components (Ψ_y and Ψ_z) as $\psi_{xn} = -\Psi_y \sin \alpha + \Psi_z \cos \alpha$.

Figure 2: Cross-section of a portion of beam shell wall with local and global coordinate system and displacement component

Substituting this and as well as Equation (1) in the above equation (2), the displacements at any point within the shell wall along its local coordinate system (x - s - n) can be expressed in terms of the global displacement components of the 1D beam as

$$\begin{aligned} u &= U + (y - n \sin \alpha) \theta_y + (z + n \cos \alpha) \theta_z + (\varphi - nq) \theta'_x, \\ v &= V \cos \alpha + W \sin \alpha - (r + n) \theta_x, \\ w &= -V \sin \alpha + W \cos \alpha + q \theta_x. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

With the beam kinematics (3), the governing equation of the axially loaded vibration beam can be derived from its total energy utilising Hamilton's principle. The total energy of a structure consists of strain energy (U), strain energy due to axial force (U_g) and kinetic energy (T) which can be used to derive the stiffness matrix $[K]$, geometric stiffness matrix $[K_g]$ and mass matrix $[M]$, respectively in a finite element analysis of the structure. As the derivation of the stiffness matrix $[K]$ has already been shown elsewhere [8], it is not repeated here. For a beam under an axial force ($P = \sigma A$) acting uniformly over its entire cross-sectional area (A), the strain energy due to the axial force may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} U_g &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V \sigma (v'^2 + w'^2) dv \\ U_g &= \frac{P}{2A} \int_V (v'^2 + w'^2) dv = \frac{P}{2A} \int_V \begin{Bmatrix} v' & w' \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} v' \\ w' \end{Bmatrix} dv = \frac{P}{2A} \int_V \{\epsilon_g\}^T \{\epsilon_g\} dv. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Using equation (3), the geometric strain vector $\{\varepsilon_g\}$ in the above equation can be written as

$$\{\varepsilon_g\} = \begin{Bmatrix} v' \\ w' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha & -(r+n) \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha & q \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} V' \\ W' \\ \theta_x' \end{Bmatrix} = [H_g] \{\bar{\varepsilon}_g\}. \quad (5)$$

The above equation (5) may be substituted in equation (4) and it leads to

$$U_g = \frac{P}{2A_V} \int_V \{\varepsilon_g\}^T \{\varepsilon_g\} dv = \frac{P}{2A_L} \int_L \{\bar{\varepsilon}_g\}^T [F_g] \{\bar{\varepsilon}_g\} dx \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } [F_g] = \int_A [H_g]^T [H_g] ds dn = \int \left(\int [H_g]^T [H_g] dn \right) ds = \int ([C_g]) ds.$$

The above equation can be used to derive the geometric stiffness matrix conveniently using finite element approximation of the geometric strain vector $\{\varepsilon_g\}$. The individual elements of the matrices $[F_g]$ and $[C_g]$ for I and box sections are explicitly given in Appendix A and Appendix B, respectively.

Now the kinetic energy of the beam having a harmonic motion may be written as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\dot{U}\}^T \rho \{\dot{U}\} dv = -\frac{\omega^2}{2} \int_V \{U\}^T \rho \{U\} dv. \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the mass density of the material, ω is the vibration frequency, $\{U\}^T = [u \ v \ w]$ (equation 3) is the displacement vector and $\{\dot{U}\} = d\{U\}/dt$ is the velocity vector. In a similar manner, the displacement vector (equation 3) can be written as

$$\{U\} = [H_m] \{\bar{u}\}. \quad (8)$$

where $[H_m]$ contains sectional parameters (x, y, n, r, q, α) whereas $\{\bar{u}\}$ contains global parameters ($U, V, W, \theta_x, \theta_y$ and θ_z) of the 1D beam. After substitution of the above equation (8) in equation (7), it can be written as

$$T = -\frac{\omega^2}{2} \int_V \{U\}^T \rho \{U\} dv = -\frac{\omega^2}{2} \int_L \{\bar{u}\}^T [F_m] \{\bar{u}\} dx \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } [F_m] = \int_A [H_m]^T \sigma [H_m] ds dn = \int \left(\int [H_m]^T \sigma [H_m] dn \right) ds = \int ([C_m]) ds.$$

For I and box section beams, all elements of the above matrices $[F_m]$ and $[C_m]$ are explicitly derived which are given in Appendix C and Appendix D.

For finite element implementation of the beam, quadratic Lagrangian interpolation functions are used for the axial deformation while cubic Hermetian interpolation functions are used for torsional deformation which will ensure the desired C^1 continuity of torsional rotation (θ) as the displacement field (equation 3) contains derivative of θ . As mentioned earlier, the bending deformations which are coupled with shear deformations and these are treated in a different manner following the concept of Sheikh [15] where the shear rotations Ψ_y and Ψ_z are adopted as field variables instead of θ_y and θ_z in addition to the bending displacements V and W . Taking a linear approximation of Ψ_y , Ψ_z and a cubic approximation of V and W , the field variables can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= a_1 + a_2x + a_3x^2 & (10) \\
 V &= a_4 + a_5x + a_6x^2 + a_7x^3 \\
 W &= a_8 + a_9x + a_{10}x^2 + a_{11}x^3 \\
 \Psi_y &= a_{12} + a_{13}x, \quad \Psi_z = a_{14} + a_{15}x \\
 \theta_x &= a_{16} + a_{17}x + a_{18}x^2 + a_{19}x^3
 \end{aligned}$$

Though Ψ_y and Ψ_z are taken as field variables, they are not used as nodal degrees of freedom. Interestingly, the corresponding nodal degrees of freedom are θ_y and θ_z which are introduced with the help of bending deformations which may be expressed using the above equations as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_y &= \Psi_y - V' = a_{12} + a_{13}x - a_5 - 2a_6x - 3a_7x^2, & (11) \\
 \theta_z &= \Psi_z - W' = a_{14} + a_{15}x - a_9 - 2a_{10}x - 3a_{11}x^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

The unknown constants ($a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_{19}$) found in Equations (10) can be replaced in terms of nodal displacement parameters by substitution of U, V, W, θ_y and θ_z (Equations 10 and 11) at all three nodes of the beam element (Fig. 1), and θ_x (Equation 10) and its derivative θ'_x at the two end nodes as

$$\{\delta\} = [R]\{a\} \text{ or } \{a\} = [R]^{-1}\{\delta\} \quad (12)$$

where $\{a\}^T = [a_1 \ a_2 \ a_3 \ \dots \ a_{19}]$, $[R]$ consists of coordinates (x values) of the 3 nodes and $\{\delta\}^T = [U_1 \ V_1 \ W_1 \ \theta_{x1} \ \theta_{y1} \ \theta_{z1} \ \theta'_{x1} \ U_2 \ V_2 \ W_2 \ \theta_{y2} \ \theta_{z2} \ U_3 \ V_3 \ W_3 \ \theta_{x3} \ \theta_{y3} \ \theta_{z3} \ \theta'_{x3}]$ is the nodal displacement vector.

With the help of Equations (10) and (12), the vector $\{\bar{\epsilon}_g\}$ as defined in Equation (5) may be expressed in terms of nodal displacement vector $\{\delta\}$ as

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}_g\} = [V' \ W' \ \theta'_x]^T = [S_g]\{a\} = [S_g][R]^{-1}\{\delta\} = [B_g]\{\delta\}. \quad (13)$$

The above equation is substituted in Equation (6) and it is rewritten as

$$U_g = \frac{P}{2A} \int_L \{\bar{\epsilon}_g\}^T [F_g] \{\bar{\epsilon}_g\} dx = \frac{P}{2A} \int_L \{\delta\}^T [B_g]^T [F_g] [B_g] \{\delta\} dx = \frac{P}{2} \{\delta\}^T [K_g] \{\delta\} \quad (14)$$

where $[K_g] = \frac{1}{A} \int_L [B_g]^T [F_g] [B_g] dx$ is the geometric stiffness matrix of a beam element.

Similarly, the vector $\{\bar{u}\}$ as defined in Equation (9) may be expressed in terms of $\{\delta\}$ with the help of Equations (10) (11) and (12) as

$$\{\bar{u}\} = [S_m]\{a\} = [S_m][R]^{-1}\{\delta\} = [B_m]\{\delta\}. \quad (15)$$

Again this equation is substituted in Equation (9) and it is rewritten as

$$T = -\frac{\omega^2}{2} \int_L \{\bar{u}\}^T [F_m] \{\bar{u}\} dx = -\frac{\omega^2}{2} \int_L \{\delta\}^T [B_m]^T [F_m] [B_m] \{\delta\} dx = -\frac{\omega^2}{2} \{\delta\}^T [M] \{\delta\} \quad (16)$$

where $[M] = \int_L [B_m]^T [F_m] [B_m] dx$ is the mass matrix of an element.

The stiffness, geometric stiffness and mass matrices of all elements are assembled together to form the form these matrices of the whole beam. Taking same notations of these assembled matrices, the governing equation of the axially loaded (P = axial compression) vibrating beams may be expressed as

$$([K] - P[K_g])\{\delta\} = \omega^2[M]\{\delta\} \quad (17)$$

This is an Eigen-value problem which is solved to get the vibration frequencies as Eigen values and modes of vibration as Eigen vectors. The buckling of these beams can also be solved by the above equation by simply dropping the mass matrix and can be rewritten as

$$[K]\{\delta\} = P_{cr}[K_g]\{\delta\} \quad (18)$$

where P_{cr} is the critical value of the axial compression P for the buckling of the beam.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the section, numerical examples of thin-walled composite beams having I and Box sections are solved using proposed model and the results obtained are validated with the analytical and numerical results available in literature.

Example 1: The problem of a simply supported thin-walled laminated composite beam having a span of 6m is studied using plane stress condition ($\sigma_s = 0$) of the plies. The beam has a double symmetric I section where both the flanges are 600mm wide and the web is 600mm deep. All the flange and web plates are made of 4 plies each 7.5mm thick (30mm total thickness) which are having 5 different ply orientations. The material used for all the plies is Graphite-epoxy and its properties are: $E_1=144\text{GPa}$, $E_2=9.65\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=G_{13}=4.14\text{GPa}$, $G_{23}=3.45\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.3$. The beam is analysed with the proposed technique using different number of elements and it is observed that the results are converged when the number of elements is 10 or more which is used to generate results in all cases. The critical buckling loads predicted by the proposed technique are presented in Table 1 along with those produced by other investigators who studied this problem earlier with their approach. The table shows that the present results have good agreement with the existing results.

Lay-ups	Machado & Cortinez [16]		Back & Will [17]		Vo and Lee [18]	Present
	No shear	With shear	ABAQUS	With shear	With shear	With shear
[0] ₄	42.11	33.18	30.78	28.85	30.38	35.51
[30/-30] _s	-	-	13.06	13.17	13.17	13.16
[45/-45] _s	4.45	4.44	4.41	4.41	4.41	4.41
[60/-60] _s	-	-	2.89	2.89	2.88	2.88
[0/90] _s	22.57	19.84	20.41	20.63	20.63	20.52

Table 1: Critical buckling load (MN) of a simply supported doubly-symmetric composite I-beam

Example 2: The behaviour of a 1m long cantilever beam having a mono-symmetric I section is investigated for 7 different stacking sequences for its laminated walls. The web of the beam is 50mm deep whereas the breadths of its top and bottom flanges are 30mm and 50mm, respectively. The web and flanges are made of 16 layers each 0.13mm thick with a symmetrical layup. The material used for all the layers is glass-epoxy having the following properties: $E_1=53.78\text{GPa}$, $E_2=17.93\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=G_{13}=8.96\text{GPa}$, $G_{23}=3.45\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.25$. The beam is analysed with the proposed approach and the critical buckling loads obtained for different ply orientations are presented in Table 2 along with those reported by Kim et al. [19], and Vo and Lee [18]. The comparison of the results shows a very good performance of the proposed element.

Lay-ups	Kim et al. [19]		Vo and Lee[18]	Present
	Abaqus	No Shear	With shear	With shear
[0] ₁₆	2969.7	2998.2	2993.2	2994.5
[15/-15] _{4s}	2790.9	2811.8	2803.6	2803.3
[30/-30] _{4s}	2190.6	2199.7	2184.7	2185.1
[45/-45] _{4s}	1558.9	1561.9	1546.0	1547.2
[60/-60] _{4s}	1239.4	1241.3	1227.8	1229.0
[75/-75] _{4s}	1132.2	1134.5	1126.7	1127.9
[0/90] _{4s}	2101.5	2113.9	2100.6	2101.8

Table 2: Critical buckling load (N) of a cantilever mono-symmetric composite I-beam

Example 3: A double symmetric I section beam clamped at its two ends is taken to study the effect of fibre orientations of one of its laminated flanges for different values of the beam length (l) with respect to the depth (d) of the web. The web and flanges are made of 2 layers where each layer has a thickness of 2.5mm (total thickness $t=5$ mm) and the following material properties: $E_1/E_2=25$, $G_{12}/E_2=0.6$, $G_{13}=G_{23}=G_{12}$, $\nu_{12}=0.25$. The layup of the top flange and the web is $[0/45^0]$ and that of the bottom flange is $[\theta]_2$ where the value of θ is varies from 0 to 90 degrees. The asymmetric laminated configuration found in this situation produces nonzero off-diagonal terms of the cross sectional stiffness matrix (F_{13} , F_{16} , F_{24} , F_{35}) which is responsible for coupling of different deformation modes. The variation of normalized critical buckling load $\bar{P} = P_{cr} l^2 / (d^3 t E_2)$ with respect to θ as predicted by the proposed model is presented in Fig. 3 for three different values of (l/d) ratio. Figure 3 shows that the critical buckling load decreases monolithically with the increase of fiber angle (θ). However, there is a small increasing tendency of this buckling load parameter (\bar{P}) for low span-to-depth ratios (l/d) when the fiber angle is ranging from 0 to 15 degrees. Also, the mode shapes for different displacement components corresponding to $\bar{P}_1 = 2.48$ ($\theta=75^\circ$, $l/d=25$) are plotted in Fig.4.

Figure 3: Variation of buckling load parameter (\bar{P}) of a clamped composite I-beam with respect to fiber angle (θ) of its bottom flange

Example 4: The buckling characteristics of a 12m long simply supported beam having a box section (300mm wide and 600mm deep) is studied for different stacking sequences of its laminated walls. In all these cases, the four laminated walls of this box section beam consist of 4 layers each having a thickness of 7.5mm. The material used for these layers is Graphite-Epoxy (AS4/3501) which is having the following properties: $E_1=144$ GPa, $E_2=9.65$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=4.14$ GPa, $G_{23}=3.45$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.3$. The lamination schemes used for all the beam walls are $[0]_4$, $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[45/-45]_{2s}$. The critical buckling loads predicted by the proposed model are presented in Table 3 along with those of

Cortinez and Piovan [20] and Kim et al. [11] (based on two techniques) which show a very good correlation between the results obtained by different techniques.

Figure 4: Mode shapes of a clamped I section composite beam ($\theta=75^\circ$ and $l/d=25$)

Lay-ups	Cortinez and Piovan [20] (no shear)	Kim et al. [21]		Present
		30 H-Beam elements (with shear)	SMM (with shear)	
[0/0/0/0]	9.33	9.35	9.35	9.00
[45/-45/-45/45]	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97
[0/90/90/0]	4.97	5.02	5.02	4.94

Table 3: Critical buckling load (MN) of a simply supported composite box-beam

Example 5: An 8m long simply supported beam having a box section (100mm width and 200mm deep) is used to study its buckling and vibration characteristics. The four walls of the beam are made of two layers each having a thickness of 2.5mm and the following material properties: $E_1/E_2=25$, $G_{12}/E_2=0.6$, $\nu_{12}=0.25$. The flanges have a stacking sequence of $[0]_2$ and that of the webs is $[\theta/-\theta]$ where the value of θ is varied from 0 to 90° with an increment of 15° . The non-dimensional critical buckling load $\bar{P} = P_{cr} l^2 / (b^3 t E_2)$ evaluated by the proposed technique and presented with those of Vo and Lee [22] in Table 4 which shows a good agreement between them.

Fiber angle	Vo and Lee [22] (with shear)	Present
0	36.009	35.509
15	29.245	28.916
30	13.549	13.479
45	7.858	7.834
60	6.670	6.653
75	6.419	6.403
90	6.375	6.359

Table 4: Normalized critical buckling load \bar{P} of a simply supported composite box-beam

The vibration analysis of this beam subjected axial load is also carried out by the proposed model where the axial load is varied from $-P_{cr}$ to P_{cr} . The variation of natural frequency for the fundamental mode with respect to the axial load is plotted in Fig. 5 for different values of θ . Figure 5 clearly shows a monotonic decrease of the vibration frequency with the increase of axial compression as expected.

Figure 5: Effects on axial load on vibration frequency of a composite box- beam

3 CONCLUSIONS

An efficient one dimensional beam element is developed for buckling and vibration analysis of thin-walled composite beams of open and closed cross sections considering axial displacement, torsion, bi-axial bending and transverse shear deformations as well as out of plane sectional warping. The cross-sectional matrices required for the formulation of geometric stiffness and mass matrices of the beam are derived analytically where all possible couplings between the abovementioned modes of deformation are considered. The effect of shear deformation of the beam walls is included which requires a C^0 continuous finite element formulation of the bending deformation coupled with the shear deformation. On the other hand, the torsional deformation requires a C^1 continuous FE formulation due to the incorporation of warping deformation. The difficulty associated with the implementation of both these formulations in the present coupled problem is successfully overcome by using a novel concept proposed by one of the authors. The proposed analysis technique is used to solve numerical examples of thin-walled laminated composite beams having open I and closed box sections taking different boundary conditions and stacking sequences of the beam walls. For the vibration analysis of beams, the effect of axial force on the frequency of vibration is also studied. In many cases, the results predicted by the proposed technique are validated with the analytical and/or numerical results available in literature. The agreement between the results is found to be very good in most of the cases which ensures the reliability and range of applicability of the proposed element. New results are also presented in this paper which should be useful to future researchers.

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APPENDIX A

The non-zero elements appeared in the upper triangle of the symmetric matrix $[C_g]$ (Equation 6) are presented in their explicit form as follows (applicable for I and box sections).

$$C_{11}^g = C_{22}^g = A_{11}, \quad C_{13}^g = -B_{11} \cos \alpha - A_{11}(q \sin \alpha + r \cos \alpha)$$

$$C_{23}^g = -B_{11} \sin \alpha + A_{11}(q \cos \alpha - r \sin \alpha), \quad C_{33}^g = C_{11} + 2rB_{11} + A_{11}(q^2 + r^2)$$

APPENDIX B

The non-zero elements appeared in the upper triangle of the symmetric matrix $[F_g]$ (Equation 6) are presented in their explicit form as follows (applicable for I section, Fig. 6a).

$$F_{11}^g = F_{22}^g = b(A_{11}^1 + A_{11}^2) + dA_{11}^3, \quad F_{13}^g = bd(A_{11}^2 - A_{11}^1)/2 - b(B_{11}^2 - B_{11}^1), \quad F_{23}^g = -dB_{11}^3$$

$$F_{33}^g = b^3(A_{11}^1 + A_{11}^2)/12 + bd^2(A_{11}^1 + A_{11}^2)/4 + bd(B_{11}^1 + B_{11}^2) + b(C_{11}^1 + C_{11}^2) + d^3A_{11}^3/12 + dC_{11}^3/12$$

Figure 6: Thin-walled beam having open and closed section

The non-zero elements appeared in the upper triangle of the symmetric matrix $[F_g]$ (Equation 6) are presented in their explicit form as follows (applicable for box section, Fig. 6b).

$$F_{11}^g = F_{22}^g = b(A_{11}^1 + A_{11}^2) + d(A_{11}^3 + A_{11}^4), \quad F_{13}^g = bd(A_{11}^2 - A_{11}^1)/2 - b(B_{11}^2 - B_{11}^1),$$

$$F_{23}^g = bd(A_{11}^4 - A_{11}^3)/2 + d(B_{11}^4 - B_{11}^3),$$

$$F_{33}^g = b^3(A_{11}^1 + A_{11}^2)/12 + bd^2(A_{11}^1 + A_{11}^2)/4 + b^2d(A_{11}^3 + A_{11}^4)/4 + bd(B_{11}^1 + B_{11}^2 + B_{11}^3 + B_{11}^4)$$

$$+ b(C_{11}^1 + C_{11}^2) + d^3(A_{11}^3 + A_{11}^4)/12 + d(C_{11}^3 + C_{11}^4)$$

APPENDIX C

The non-zero elements appeared in the upper triangle of the symmetric matrix $[C_m]$ (Equation 6) are presented in their explicit form as follows (applicable for I and box sections).

$$C_{11}^m = C_{22}^m = C_{33}^m = A, \quad C_{15}^m = Ay, \quad C_{16}^m = Az, \quad C_{17}^m = A\phi, \quad C_{24}^m = -A(q \sin \alpha + r \cos \alpha),$$

$$C_{34}^m = A(q \cos \alpha - r \sin \alpha), \quad C_{44}^m = A(q^2 + r^2) + C/12, \quad C_{55}^m = Ay^2 + C \sin^2 \alpha / 12,$$

$$C_{56}^m = Ayz - C \sin(2\alpha) / 24, \quad C_{57}^m = Ay\phi + Cq \sin \alpha / 12, \quad C_{66}^m = Az^2 + C \cos^2 \alpha / 12,$$

$$C_{67}^m = Az\phi - Cq \cos \alpha / 12, \quad C_{77}^m = A\phi^2 + Cq^2 / 12$$

where $A = \sum t_i \rho_i$, $B = \sum t_i^2 \rho_i$ and $C = \sum t_i^3 \rho_i$

APPENDIX D

The non-zero elements appeared in the upper triangle of the symmetric matrix $[F_m]$ (Equation 9) are presented in their explicit form as follows (applicable for I section, Fig. 6a).

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{11}^m &= F_{22}^g = F_{33}^g = b_1 A_1 + b_2 A_2 + d A_3, \quad F_{16}^m = -F_{24}^m = d(b_1 A_1 - b_2 A_2)/2, \\
F_{44}^m &= (b_1^3 A_1 + b_2^3 A_2 + d^3 A_3)/12 + d^2(b_1 A_1 + b_2 A_2)/4 + (b_1 C_1 + b_2 C_2 + d C_3)/12, \\
F_{55}^m &= (b_1^3 A_1 + b_2^3 A_2)/12 + d C_3/3, \quad F_{57}^m = d(b_1^3 A_1 - b_2^3 A_2)/24, \\
F_{66}^m &= d^3 A_3/12 + d^2(b_1 A_1 + b_2 A_2)/4 + (b_1 C_1 + b_2 C_2)/3, \quad F_{77}^m = d^2(b_1^3 A_1 + b_2^3 A_2)/48 + d^3 C_3/36
\end{aligned}$$

The non-zero elements appeared in the upper triangle of the symmetric matrix $[F_m]$ (Equation 9) are presented in their explicit form as follows (applicable for box section, Fig. 6b).

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{11}^m &= F_{22}^g = F_{33}^g = b(A_1 + A_2) + d(A_3 + A_4), \quad F_{15}^m = F_{34}^m = bd(A_4 - A_3)/2, \\
F_{16}^m &= -F_{24}^m = bd(A_1 - A_2)/2, \\
F_{44}^m &= [b^3(A_1 + A_2) + d^3(A_3 + A_4)]/12 + bd[d(A_1 + A_2) + b(A_3 + A_4)]/4 + [b(C_1 + C_2) + d(C_3 + C_4)]/12, \\
F_{55}^m &= b^3(A_1 + A_2)/12 + b^2 d(A_3 + A_4)/4 + d(C_3 + C_4)/3, \quad F_{57}^m = b^3 d(A_1 - A_2)/24, \\
F_{66}^m &= d^3(A_3 + A_4)/12 + bd^2(A_1 + A_2)/4 + b(C_1 + C_2)/3, \quad F_{67}^m = \beta bd^3(A_4 - A_3)/24, \\
F_{77}^m &= \beta^2 b^2 d^2 [b(A_1 + A_2) + d(A_3 + A_4)]/48 + \beta^2 [b^3(C_1 + C_2) + d^3(C_3 + C_4)]/144 \\
&\quad - \beta [b^3(C_1 + C_2) - d^3(C_3 + C_4)]/72 + [b^3(C_1 + C_2) - d^3(C_3 + C_4)]/144
\end{aligned}$$